
ANXIETY OUTCOME MODELLING WITH PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION-BASED SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE FUNCTION

Adegoke A. Israel

Federal University of Technology, Minna
adegoke.m1701038@st.futminna.edu.ng

Yekeen Adebayo Ibraheem

Federal University of Technology, Minna
yekeen.m1704427@st.futminna.edu.ng

Abstract

Anxiety disorder is a mental health condition marked by persistent feelings of worry, fear, or anxiety that can interfere with daily activities. It represents a global public health concern, necessitating effective assessment and intervention strategies. Recently, machine learning techniques have garnered attention for their potential to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of diagnostic and prognostic procedures. This paper presents a brilliant methodology for assessing anxiety outcomes leveraging a Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)-tuned Support Vector Machine (SVM) approach. The proposed framework integrates the PSO optimisation with SVM, a robust machine-learning algorithm known for its capability to handle complex classification tasks. The model aims to enhance its generalisation ability and improve classification accuracy in identifying anxiety outcomes by tuning the SVM parameters through PSO optimisation. We validated using a comprehensive dataset comprising individuals of over 700 sample cases with varying levels of anxiety symptoms, as measured by standardised clinical assessment tools. Through rigorous experimentation and cross-validation techniques, the performance of the PSO-tuned SVM model is evaluated against existing benchmarks and alternative machine-learning approaches. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology in accurately assessing anxiety outcomes evaluated over the accuracy, Precision, Area under Curve (AUC), Recall, and F1-score, showcasing superior performance compared to traditional SVM models and even other current techniques as of the time of writing with over 90% in each case of evaluation.

Keywords: Anxiety, Machine Learning, Particle Swarm Optimization, Support vector Classifier, Support vector Machine, Optimization

1 Introduction

Anxiety is not the same as fear, but they are frequently utilised and traded. Anxiety is considered a future-oriented, long-acting reaction broadly centred on a diffuse danger. At the same time, fear is a suitable, present-oriented, and short-lived reaction to an identifiable and particular risk (Alan *et al.*, 2000). In 2020, many trusted that COVID-19 would be over in 2021 and ordinary life would continue. The circumstance is distinctive: the widespread is still progressing with novel and more infectious variations driving expanded contamination rates over the globe, with subsequently more rigid limitations in social intuition and more lockdowns. By the spring of 2021, over 156 million affirmed cases and more than 3.2 million passing COVID-19 have been detailed by the World Health Organization in healthcare frameworks around the world being overburdened at certain times (Manchia *et al.*, 2022). The COVID-19 widespread has cleared through the globe rapidly and aimlessly. Government limitations put in put to moderate the spread of the infection have driven far-reaching social confinement, which can have significant results on mental well-being (Magson *et al.*, 2021). In Nigeria, a country that faced its unique set of challenges during the pandemic, the toll on mental health was particularly severe. The lockdowns, economic hardship, and uncertainty about the future exacerbated anxiety levels among the population. However, as we transition into a post-COVID-19 era, technology presents new opportunities to address these mental health issues and improve life expectancy. It is widely recognized that technology has played a crucial role in addressing various challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic and has the potential to continue making a positive effect in the post-COVID-19 time. For example, the function of e-learning technologies has allowed schools and educational institutions to continue providing instruction during the pandemic. Technology can facilitate social connections and combat loneliness and isolation, which are factors that can impact mental health and well-being. Digital platforms and AI can potentially improve access to mental well-being administrations and bolster, especially in remote or underserved areas. The development of digital health solutions and telemedicine has expanded access to healthcare services, including mental health support (Dorothee *et al.*, 2020). This research aims to explore the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in assessing anxiety levels among Nigerians. By leveraging AI technology, we can develop a more accessible and proactive approach to mental health monitoring and support. This project seeks to understand how machine learning can be harnessed to combat the decline in life expectancy by addressing anxiety and stress-related health issues among the Nigerian population.

2 Related works, Motivation and Overview

Anxiety deteriorates human health and often leads to death if unaddressed. Unfortunately, anxiety is difficult to diagnose. This is because the physical symptoms of anxiety are not always obvious, as they often develop imperceptibly. The latter COVID-19 has activated a surge in anxiety around the globe. Much of the public's behavioral and passionate reaction to the infection can be caught through the system of dread administration hypothesis, which proposes that fear of passing drives much of human

behaviour. Fear of passing has as of late appeared to foresee not as it were anxiety related to COVID-19 but too to play a causal part in different mental well-being conditions (Menzies, 2020). It is imperative to address this critical issue and explore innovative solutions that leverage Artificial Intelligence (AI) for the assessment of anxiety. By doing so, we aim to improve accessibility, early detection, and intervention for anxiety disorders, ultimately mitigating the factors contributing to the decline in life expectancy. Notwithstanding clear concerns, AI applications in medication are relentlessly expanding. As mental well-being professionals, we ought to familiarize ourselves with AI, get its current and future uses, and arrange to work with AI because it enters the clinical standard (Sarah *et al.*, 2019). My purpose of the study is to assess anxiety outcomes using particle swarm optimization – tuned survey vector machine approach

The point of this study is to predict anxiety assessment outcomes through the use of a particle swarm optimization-tuned support vector machine approach. This aim is achieved by the following objectives: To determine important features influencing or contributing to anxiety tendency aggravation in persons, process these features in other to realize a feature target mapping, and predict anxiety treatment status based on these features using a machine learning approach specifically the support vector machine. And finally to realise a better performing model with the help of a PSO-tuned hyper-parameter model

The importance of this research lies in its potential to address a pressing issue: the decline in life expectancy. More than 1.8 million lives are assessed to have been misplaced due to COVID-19 around the world in 2020. This estimate—although staggering—masks the uneven effect of the widespread over distinctive nations and statistic characteristics like age and sex, as well as its effect on populace wellbeing, a long time of life misplaced and life span (Manuel *et al.*, 2022).

By developing an AI-driven approach to assess anxiety and stress levels, we hope to contribute to improving mental health, thereby enhancing overall well-being and life expectancy. This research may serve as a blueprint for utilizing AI technology to combat anxiety-related health problems in the aftermath of a major public health crisis in Nigeria. The inspiration behind this study stems from the emergency need to address the escalating issue of anxiety, exacerbated by the worldwide COVID-19 widespread, and effect the worldwide COVID-19 widespread, and on mental health, well-being, and ultimately life expectancy. Recognizing anxiety as a pervasive and challenging condition to diagnose, the research aims to leverage the power of Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifically employing a Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)-tuned Support Vector Machine (SVM) approach. By delving deep into the assessment of anxiety levels among Nigerians, the study seeks to identify influential features contributing to anxiety tendencies, map these features to treatment outcomes, and predict anxiety treatment status using machine learning. The overarching goal is to develop an innovative, AI-driven solution that enhances accessibility, early detection, and intervention for anxiety disorders, thereby contributing to the improvement of mental health, and overall well-being, and potentially addressing the decline in life expectancy. The study's significance lies in its potential to offer a blueprint for the

application of AI in combating anxiety-related health challenges, particularly in the aftermath of a major public health crisis like the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria.

The prevalence of anxiety disorders has increased worldwide, overcoming national and cultural barriers. These illnesses have a significant impact on people's mental health, cognitive functions, behaviour, and social interactions, among other aspects of their lives. Anxiety disorders throw off the delicate balance of mental health. They can appear in a variety of ways, from acute panic attacks to chronic anxiety, and they eventually change how people think and act (Nemesure *et al.*, 2021). Wide-ranging effects result from these modifications to thinking and behaviour patterns, such as deterioration in interpersonal and professional social interactions and relationships. The overall effect is a noticeable decline in the impacted individuals' quality of life. The 2017 National Health and Morbidity Survey (NHMS), while mainly centred on Malaysia, provides important perspectives on the global problem of anxiety disorders. Despite the survey's focus on Malaysia, its results highlight how widespread this mental health problem is. According to the survey, one in five individuals in Malaysia endures misery, which frequently coexists with anxiety disorders and worsens people's quality of life overall. Furthermore, anxiety is reported by two out of every five Malaysians, highlighting the seriousness and prevalence of this mental health problem. In addition, the survey indicates that 10% of the population has concerns about stress. Although stress is a normal reaction to life's obstacles, it can seriously jeopardize one's emotional and mental health when it continues unchecked and becomes a chronic illness (Shafiee, 2020). Numerous studies have shown that students in higher education are especially vulnerable to mental health problems like anxiety and depression. Students in higher education encounter a variety of difficulties, including those related to their changing lifestyles, social adjustments, and academic responsibilities. Finding the factors that contribute to these problems is a difficult task for academics and higher education institutions. These results make it very clear that novel strategies are desperately needed to prevent and treat anxiety disorders. The creation and application of cutting-edge techniques that provide early detection and customized interventions are necessary in this context with the extreme objective of progressing the quality of life for individuals impacted. This objective is in line with the larger global mission to effectively and comprehensively address the growing problem of mental health disorders (Priya *et al.*, 2020).

2.4 Related Work

Pandit *et al.*, (2023) introduce in their paper work titled Examining Factors for Anxiety and Depression Prediction. As one of the mental health conditions, and as an open well-being concern thahasve fundamental impacts on all people's quality of life, relationship with others, and by and large prosperity. In early inquiries about work machine learning methods and information science have coordinated the imperative devices for early discovery of mental wellbeing-related issues. The researcher's objective is to point out more information on the components driving anxiety and depression and to develop a predictive model for improving the accuracy and efficiency of early mental health diagnoses. Out of the

methods that have been used Tabular DNN outperformed ANN and other machine learning methods that were used by 30%. Furthermore, the findings were able to prove that deep learning tabular models have the strength to improve accuracy and efficiency. A diagnosis of mental health at an early stage is very important to have access and support for all individuals who need this work.

According to (Kotsilieris *et al.*, 2020) Anxiety disorder is the biggest group and the foremost commonest sort of mental health disorder. Along the line, it has been known that checking patients' histories and analysing issue impersonation in making coherent choices can be done by the use of a machine learning approach. The survey of this paper is the most concepts and applications of machine learning strategies in anticipating anxiety disorder sorts and Seventeen (17) thinks about were considered that connected machine learning approach for anticipating anxiety disarranges and five (5) extra considers were inspected for anticipating suicide propensities. The precision of comes about varies depending on the sort of uneasy clutter and the sort of strategies utilized for foreseeing the clutter.

The side effects of anxiety and depression at an early stage in children have 4 major impacts on children's mental well-being development counting their full advancement. Examining the impact of mental well-being issues on emotional advancement has drawn the intrigue of most researchers considered for the final two decades. The objective of this paper, machine learning strategies was utilized to foresee the chance variables related to children's in school on depression and anxiety.

Qasrawi *et al.*, (2022), utilize data consisting of 5685 understudies in grades 5-9, matured 10-17 a long time, examining at open and outcast schools in the West Bank. The information was collected utilizing the wellbeing behaviours school children survey within the 2012-2013 scholarly a long time and analyzed utilizing machine learning to anticipate the hazard components related to understudy mental wellbeing side effects. Five machine learning techniques (Arbitrary Woodland, Neural Arrange, Choice Tree, Bolster Vector Machine, and Naïve Bayes) were utilized for the forecast by the analysts. Out of the five machine learning strategies that were utilized they come about demonstrated that the Arbitrary Woodland show had the most noteworthy exactness levels (72.6%, 68.5%) for depression and anxiety respectively and it has the most excellent execution in gathering and foreseeing the student's depression and anxiety. The results showed that school viciousness and bullying, scholarly execution, and family wage were the foremost imperative variables influencing depression and anxiety scales. In general, machine learning demonstrated to be a proficient device for recognizing and anticipating the related components that impact understudy sadness and anxiety. The arrangement of machine learning inside the school data frameworks might encourage the improvement of health prevention and intercession programs that will enhance students' mental health and cognitive improvement.

In the research work of (Priya *et al.*, 2020) machine learning calculations were utilized to foresee the event of anxiety, depression, and stretch. The analysts collected information from utilized and unemployed people from diverse societies and communities utilizing the Depression, Anxiety, and Push

Scale survey. The machine learning calculations precisely anticipated uneasiness, discouragement, and stretch on five diverse seriousness levels. In any case, the classes in the perplexity lattice were imbalanced, so the F1 score degree was included to recognize the finest exactness demonstrated. The Random Forest classifier was found to be the foremost among the five calculations utilized. Also, the calculations were particularly sensitive to negative comes about, as shown by the specificity parameter.

Shafie *et al.*, (2020) introduce that mental health problems have become a significant concern in Malaysia. Generally, these problems encompass a range of health issues that impact an individual's emotions, thoughts, behaviour, and social interactions. The National Wellbeing and Morbidity Study (NHMS) conducted in 2017 revealed that one out of every five Malaysians suffers from depression, while two out of every five experience anxiety, and one out of every ten faces stress. Notably, higher education students are particularly vulnerable to mental health issues. However, identifying the factors contributing to these problems poses a challenge, hindering effective assistance for individuals affected by them.

Sekulić *et al.*, (2019) introduce that understanding and addressing mental health issues is crucial for the overall well-being of society. By analyzing text data from sources like social media, researchers can gain deeper insights into these illnesses and potentially detect them early on. In our research, we aim to detect the mental state of social media users using advanced deep learning models, departing from traditional methods. Through a binary classification task, we successfully predict if a user is suffering from one of nine different disorders. Our hierarchical attention network surpasses previous benchmarks for four of these disorders. Additionally, we investigate the limitations of our model and examine key phrases that contribute to the classification through word-level attention weights analysis.

According to Kumar *et al.*, (2020), there has been a noteworthy rise within the predominance of psychological disorders around the world. This considers points to foresee the event of common mental well-being issues, counting anxiety, depression, and stretch, by utilizing eight diverse machine learning calculations. Information from the online DASS42 apparatus was utilized to anticipate five levels of severity for each clutter. The calculations were categorized into probabilistic, closest neighbour, neural organize, and tree-based strategies. Furthermore, a cross-breed classification calculation was utilized to foresee the severity levels. The same methods were connected to another dataset, DASS21, collected by the creators. The results show that the crossover calculation outperformed person calculations in terms of expectation precision. Strikingly, the spiral premise work arranges a sort of neural arrangement and displays the most elevated exactness among the calculations utilized. The researcher discusses the significance of early detection and prediction of lung cancer, by emphasizing the potential of machine learning-based models, specifically ensemble techniques, to enhance the accuracy in predicting lung cancer.

Mamun *et al.*, (2022) review existing research on lung cancer prediction models and introduce newly developed ensemble learning techniques. The researchers considered using a dataset of 309 individuals by examining their attributes such as age, smoking habits, and various health factors. As a result, the researcher identified that the XGboost technique outperformed other ensemble methods, achieving impressive accuracy, precision, recall, and AUC scores of 94.42%, 95.66%, 94.46%, and 98.14%, respectively. Based on the research work of Diep *et al.*, (2022), the researcher discusses how traditional screening methods for anxiety and depression can be limiting and how the recent advancements in Natural Language Processing (NLP) and speech modelling offer a more effective approach in addressing the situation. The proposal introduces a multi-modal system that combines deep-learned features from audio and text with hand-crafted features rooted in clinical domain knowledge for screening depression and anxiety. However, the experimental results indicate that the integration of deep-learned features with hand-crafted techniques improved the classification performance, which demonstrates the potential of speech-based biomarkers for mental health screening in the realm of digital health, based on the F1 scores increasing from 0.58 to 0.63 for depression and from 0.54 to 0.57 for anxiety.

George *et al.*, (2021) discuss anxiety as a response to life's stresses and clashes, with over-the-top signs demonstrating anxiety disorders regularly related to Autonomic dysfunction (ADy). Recognizing ADy inside uneasiness clutter patients utilizing existing strategies is considered a challenging assignment. The analysts receive machine learning models and properties determined from ECG and respiratory signals to identify ADy in people with anxiety. Factual and recurrence space highlights from these signals are utilized, and machine learning calculations, counting SVM, Irregular Timberland, and Slope Boosting. Based on the try conducted the accomplish promising comes about with precision up to 82.2% and AUC values up to 0.84 in 10 and 30 miniature sectioned datasets. Based on the discoveries the analysts recommended that ECG-derived highlights can serve as successful markers for diagnosing ADy in anxiety clutter patients, and the potential for even better precision with profound neural network-based models is famous for assisting investigation.

Wei *et al.*, (2023) address the centrality of screening and diagnosing anxiety and depression in epilepsy patients, given their high predominance as comorbidities. The analysts enlist 480 epilepsy patients and utilize six machine learning models to foresee anxiety and depression. The results collated by the analyst show that the random forest and multilayer perceptron models are especially compelling in expectation, with stigma being the foremost imperative highlight. The study proposes that the strategies created may be profitable for distinguishing epilepsy patients at risk of anxiety and discouragement, possibly supporting regular persistent administration. Further research is required to evaluate the commonsense application of this framework in clinical settings.

Table 2.1 Overview of Existing Work

Author/ Year	Title	Problem statement	Methodology	Result	Limitation
Pandit <i>et al.</i> , (2023)	Examining Factors for Anxiety and Depression Prediction	Anxiety is one of the mental well-being conditions, and as a public well-being concern, it has a basic impact on all people's quality of life, relationships with others, and general prosperity.	The researcher adopted ANN, DNN and other machine-learning methods	The result obtained by the researcher shows that Tabular DNN perform 40% better compared to ANN and other machine learning model	Anxiety, depression and stress levels were only considered by the researchers.
Kotsilieri <i>s et al.</i> , (2020)	Foreseeing Anxiety Disorders and suicide inclination utilising machine learning: an audit	Anxiety disorder is the biggest group and the foremost common sort of mental well-being disorder. Along the line, it has been known that checking patients' history and diagnosis	Machine learning technique for predicting anxiety disorder type	The exactness of the results contrasts according to the sort of anxiety clutter. The Hybrid strategies perform way better than other methods with 33.3% lead	--
Qasrawi <i>et al</i> .,(2021)	Schoolchildren's Depression and Anxiety Risk Components Evaluation and Expectation: Machine Learning Procedures	Analysts distinguish that depression and anxiety have a big impact on children at an early organize.	The study is conducted at the public and refugee West Bank school, and a survey is conducted using questions to collect data, which is later utilised to	Based on the experimental result the researchers identify that Random Forest performs best in terms of accuracy of 72% and 68.5% for depression and anxiety.	Limitation in the number of variables considered in the analysis.

	Execution Analysis			conduct an exploratory investigation on different machine learning algorithms such as NB, DT, SVM, RF and NN		
Priya <i>et al.</i> , (2020b)	Anticipating Anxiety, Depression and Stress in Cutting edge Life Utilizing Machine Learning Calculations	Due to modern work, the community is facing a high growth rate of anxiety, stress and depression.	The study proposed a machine- learning algorithm	The experimental result shows that random forests perform best in terms of classification.	The experimental analysis was limited to 5 machine-learning algorithms.	
Shafiee, and Mutalib, (2020)	Expectation of Mental well- being issues among Higher Instruction Understudy Utilizing Machine Learning	In Malaysia, it recognises the national well-being and dreariness overview that one out of five people is depressed.	The researcher adopted a machine- learning algorithm	The researcher achieves 70% to 96% accuracy using the SVM algorithm.	The experimental study is limited to Malaysia country only	
Kumar <i>et al.</i> , (2020b)	Evaluation of Anxiety, Depression and Stress utilizing Machine Learning Models	Researchers identify that psychological health issues as become frequent in today's world.	The researchers adopt, four categories of algorithm, including nearest neighbour, probabilistic,	The result shows that the hybrid algorithm performs better than the single algorithm.	The researcher focuses only on Anxiety, Depression and Stress.	

			neural network and tree-based.		
Mamun <i>et al.</i> , (2022)	Lung cancer expectations show utilizing outfit learning methods and an orderly survey examination	Lung cancer is a highly malignant disease with metastatic potential, which requires early detection to improve patient survival.	The creators present unused gathering learning strategies and analyze a dataset of 309 people considering different properties	The XGBoost ensemble technique outperformed others, achieving remarkable accuracy (94.42%), precision (95.66%), recall (94.46%), and AUC (98.14%) scores.	The study is constrained by its focus on specific attributes and dataset characteristics, potentially limiting its generalizability. Further validation and diverse dataset usage are essential.
Diep <i>et al.</i> , (2022)	Multi-modal profound learning framework for depression and anxiety discovery	Conventional strategies for screening anxiety and depression are insufficient, and there's a requirement for more successful approaches.	The researcher proposed a multi-modal system which combines deep-learned highlights from audio and text with hand-crafted highlights based on clinical space knowledge to screen for depression and anxiety.	An improvement in the classification F1 score, with an increase from 0.58 to 0.63 for depression and from 0.54 to 0.57 for anxiety.	Potential constraints identified in the research work include dataset size, generalizability, and the need for further validation and clinical testing.

George <i>et al.</i> , (2021)	Anticipating Autonomic Brokenness in Anxiety Clutter from ECG and Respiratory Signals Utilizing Machine Learning Models	The researchers identified the challenge of detecting Autonomic dysfunction (ADy) in individuals with anxiety disorders.	The research adopts ECG and respiratory signal analysis, extracting statistical and frequency domain features. Directed machine learning models, counting SVM, Random Forest, and Slope Boosting, are utilised for classification	The researcher's work obtains the highest accuracy of 82.2%, and AUC values up to 0.84 for 10 and 30-minute segmented datasets, demonstrating the potential of ECG-derived features for ADy diagnosis.	The limitations identified include dataset size, generalizability, and the need for further validation, particularly when implementing deep neural network-based models.
Wei <i>et al.</i> , (2023)	Utilising Machine Learning approach to anticipate depression and anxiety among patients with epilepsy in China: A cross-sectional Study	The study centres on the significance of precisely foreseeing anxiety and depression, predominant co-morbidities among epilepsy patients, for their viable administration, highlighting the requirement for progressed prediction strategies.	Machine learning models were utilized to anticipate anxiety and depression	The study found that random forest and multilayer perceptron models performed well in anticipating anxiety and sadness. Include significance analysis revealed that stigma played a significant role. The results were similar for both anxiety and	Advanced research is required to survey the viable application of this framework in clinical settings.

2.2 Machine Learning Approaches

As discussed earlier, anxiety disorders are a worldwide issue that negatively affects people's quality of life and calls for efficient early identification and specialized treatments. The application of machine learning technologies have since offered a paradigm shift in the field of mental health prediction to address this challenge. These cutting-edge techniques have the potential to completely transform how we recognize and treat anxiety disorders, which would have many positive effects. The ability to achieve early detection is one of the main benefits of machine learning for anxiety prediction. We can predict anxiety at different levels of severity thanks to machine learning algorithms, as shown by research by (Priya *et al.*, 2020) and (Nemesure *et al.* 2022). The objective of improving the quality of life for those impacted by anxiety disorders is closely aligned with the early detection that is essential for prompt interventions and customized treatment plans. As is often the case in the literature, it lessens the severity of these conditions and provides access to more potent therapeutic approaches.

2.2.1 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

This potent formula is well-known in favour of how well it performs in classification applications. We will use its high-dimensional data handling and complex pattern recognition skills to great effect in our anxiety prediction model (Islam *et al.*, 2020). Support Vector Machine (SVM) is another famous contemporary machine learning reach. SVM are directed learning models that look at information for relapse and classification alongside related learning procedures. Employing a strategy known as the "kernel trick," SVMs can successfully conduct non-linear classification in expansion to linear classification by certainly deciphering their inputs into high-dimensional include spaces. In quintessence, it draws borders between the different classes (Mahesh *et al.*, 2018).

2.2.2 Random Forest Classifier

In other to improve prediction accuracy, the Random Forest algorithm provides an ensemble approach that combines several decision trees. This approach works especially well for our task because it is highly accurate and proficient with structured data. The Random Forest (RF) formula is a classification technique employed for classifying sentiment analysis and emotion analysis by adopting significant datasets. Random Forest operates by amalgamating tree structures and training on the available sample data to perform classification(Saifullah *et al.*, 2021).

2.2.3 Logistic Regression (LR)

For tasks involving binary classification, logistic regression (LR) is a basic yet effective algorithm. It is a good option for the preliminary investigation of anxiety prediction due to its interpretability and simplicity. According to (Widodo *et al.*, 2022), logistic regression is utilized to portray information and clarify the relationship between one subordinate parallel variable and one or more free factors that are ostensible, ordinal, interim, or proportion. The most fundamental classification algorithm is LR. In terms of mathematics, LR functions similarly to linear regression. To optimize model correctness, LR determines the proper weights or coefficients for each column (Wade *et al.*, 2020).

2.2.4 Decision Tree

Decision Tree modelling offers simplicity and transparency. These trees are an effective resource for learning about the elements that lead to anxiety disorders. They will support our efforts to develop novel approaches and deeper comprehension. One of the effective techniques that is frequently applied in many domains, including machine learning, picture preparation, and design acknowledgement, is the decision tree (Stein *et al.*, 2005). DT could be a consecutive show that viably and cohesively combines several crucial tests in which a numerical include is compared to edge esteem in each test. Compared to the numerical weights within the neural network of associations between hubs, the conceptual rules are considerably less complex to make. DT is utilized generally for gathering purposes. Moreover, DT could be a classification show that's habitually utilized in information mining (Rana *et al.*, 2020). Each tree is made up of hubs and branches. Each subset indicates an esteem that can be taken by each hub, which speaks to highlights in a category that should be classified (Charbuty *et al.* 2021).

3 Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

The dataset utilized in this study starts from undergraduate students at the College of Lahore, giving profitable experiences into the predominant issues of depression and anxiety among the student populace. Collected from 787 members, the dataset is motivated by the Beck Depression and Beck Uneasiness inventories, two broadly utilized measures for evaluating mental well-being.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

Before actualizing a machine learning process, it is basic to embrace data preprocessing. This step is significant as different models have unmistakable prerequisites and information quality can essentially affect prescient execution. Information preprocessing serves a few key purposes, counting information cleansing and planning to relieve inclinations, taking care of lost values, and diminishing variety. The dataset includes both numerical and categorical information, requiring the encoding of categorical factors sometime recently they can be utilized for modelling purposes. Also, the information experienced exception location and evacuation to dispense with information focus that might

antagonistically influence demonstrate execution. Guaranteeing that autonomous factors are inside the same extent is crucial for showing stability; hence, highlight scaling was connected to standardize the factors. This was done to relieve any potential inclinations and overfitting within the preparation of our machine-learning model. The execution of these preprocessing assignments was encouraged utilizing the Python information control library, pandas, and the machine learning library, sci-kit-learn. The step-by-step preparation is outlined in Figure 3.3.

Fig. 3.1 The Data Preprocessing Stages Taken

The categories of the class of data captured are represented by percentage in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Dataset split by percentages per class

Data Set	Proportion %
Moderate	38.7
Mild	36.3
Severe	15.8
None- Minimal	8.43
Missing rows	0.76

3.3 Model Development and Training

The essential objective of a machine learning demonstration is to use past encounters and procured information to viably produce modern occasions. To evaluate the model's execution, it is standard to conduct assessments on a subset of the whole dataset, where the show experiences preparing on this subset, and the remaining parcel is utilized to gauge the model's adequacy. Within the setting of this think about, our dataset was isolated in a 70:30 proportion, with 70% dedicated to preparing the demonstration and the remaining 30% designated for assessing the model's execution. These parameters, frequently alluded to as hyperparameters, are decided amid the model training phase and play a vital part in distinguishing the foremost appropriate demonstration for machine learning tasks. Assist subtle elements concerning the points of interest of hyperparameters will be explained within the ensuing subsection of this think.

3.6 Hyperparameter Tuning

Upon building a machine learning model, determining the optimal architecture becomes a critical task, involving various design choices. Often, it is challenging to discern the ideal architecture for a given model upfront, prompting the need to explore a range of possibilities. In a well-structured machine learning approach, the exploration of model architectures is ideally delegated to the machine itself, allowing it to autonomously identify the optimal configuration. The parameters responsible for defining the model's architecture are termed hyperparameters, and the process of searching for the ideal model architecture is known as hyperparameter tuning (Chong *et al.*, 2022). These hyperparameters play an essential part in tending to principal demonstrate plan questions, such as the polynomial degree for direct models, the admissible least and most extreme profundity for a choice tree, the number of trees in a random forest, the profundity of neural arrange layer arrangements, and the learning rate for slope plunge. Within the setting of this consideration, we performed hyperparameter tuning for our best show,

consolidating a 3-fold cross-validation approach amid the lattice look to anticipate overfitting. Throughout this hyperparameter tuning process, we utilized a Python work called GridsearchCV. Our particular hyperparameter settings included `n_estimators` set to 100, a learning rate of 0.1, the greatest profundity extending from 4 to 8, and the least test leaf values traversing from 4 to 6. Be that as it may, rather than depending on a framework look, an elective and viable approach to hyperparameter tuning is the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) optimizer. PSO could be a metaheuristic optimization calculation motivated by the social behaviour of fowls and angles. Within the setting of machine learning, PSO offers an energetic and proficient strategy for looking hyper parameter spaces. The calculation imitates the collective insights of a swarm, permitting particles (arrangements) to iteratively investigate the hyperparameter space to discover ideal arrangements. By actualizing the PSO optimizer instead of the grid search, we will tackle its versatile and exploratory nature to productively explore the hyperparameter space. PSO powerfully alters the positions of particles based on their personal and collective encounters, viably meeting toward ideal hyperparameter setups. This approach provides a more versatile and possibly faster elective to conventional framework look strategies (Kilichev *et al.*, 2023).

3.6.1 Particle Swarm Optimizer

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is a nature-inspired metaheuristic optimization calculation established within the collective behaviour of social living beings, especially birds and angels. Presented by Kennedy and Eberhart in 1995, PSO has picked up noticeable quality as a capable optimization procedure broadly utilized in different spaces, counting machine learning. The calculation models the optimization handle as a swarm of particles moving through a multidimensional look space, where each particle represents a potential arrangement. In each emphasis, particles powerfully alter their positions based on their encounters and the collective data shared inside the swarm. This collaborative development is impacted by two essential components: personal best (best) and worldwide best (gbest). The pbest indicates the leading arrangement a particle has encountered, whereas the gbest speaks to the finest solution identified by any particle in the entire swarm. Through this interplay of personal and global knowledge, PSO aims to explore the solution space effectively (Hong *et al.*, 2023). The movement of each particle is guided by its current position, velocity, and the influence of the pbest and gbest. The velocity determines the direction and distance of a particle's movement in the search space. The updating of positions and velocities is governed by mathematical equations that incorporate inertia, cognitive, and social components. The inertia term maintains the current velocity, while the cognitive and social components, influenced by the particle's personal best and the swarms' global best, guide the particle toward promising regions. This combination of exploration (global best) and exploitation (personal best) ensures a balanced search for optimal solutions. One of the notable strengths of PSO lies in its simplicity and ease

of implementation (Hong et al., 2023). The algorithm's ability to adapt dynamically to changing landscapes makes it suitable for optimizing complex, non-linear functions. In the context of machine learning, PSO is employed for hyperparameter tuning, feature selection, and model optimization. Machine learning practitioners favour PSO for its efficiency in navigating high-dimensional spaces, resilience to getting stuck in local optima, and versatility across different optimization problems. Despite its widespread use, ongoing research explores enhancements and hybridizations with other optimization techniques to further improve PSO's performance in addressing diverse and challenging optimization tasks. The algorithm is designed to find the optimal solution to a given problem by iteratively adjusting a population of potential solutions, referred to as particles, based on their individual and collective experiences. Two iterative steps are involved (Zhao *et al.*, 2020).

i. Velocity Update:

$$V_{ij}(t + 1) = w \cdot v_{ij}(t) + c_1 \cdot r_1 \cdot (p_{ij} - x_{ij}(t)) + c_2 \cdot r_2 \cdot (g_{ij} - x_{ij}(t)) \quad 3.1$$

Where:

V_{ij} is the velocity of the particle (i) in dimension (j) at iteration($t + 1$),

w , is the inertia weight,

c_1 and c_2 are acceleration coefficients,

r_1 and r_2 are random numbers in the range [0, 1],

p_{ij} the best position of the particle (i) in dimension (j) (personal best),

x_{ij} the current position of the particle (i) in dimension (j) at iteration (t),

g_{ij} is the best position among all particles in dimension (j) (global best).

ii. Position Update:

$$x_{ij}(t + 1) = x_{ij}(t) + v_{ij}(t + 1) \quad 3.2$$

The Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) mimics the social behaviour of birds and fish to optimize solutions. Each potential solution, represented by a particle, adjusts its position and velocity iteratively based on its personal best and the best position found by the entire swarm. The algorithm efficiently explores the solution space, seeking the optimal solution to a given problem. PSO is widely used in various optimization tasks, such as parameter tuning in machine learning models, and it is known for

its simplicity and effectiveness in finding near-optimal solutions in complex search spaces (Kong *et al.*, 2019).

4 Finding and Discussion

4.1 Metrics

Assessing the performance of machine learning algorithms stands as a pivotal facet of any practical project endeavour. It provides insights into the effectiveness of each algorithm, delineating those that yield satisfactory outcomes from those that do not. While accuracy is often employed as a gauge for model performance in classification algorithms, it's important to note that it's not the sole determinant of a model's quality. In this study, we utilized a range of evaluation metrics, including F1-Score, Precision, Recall, Confusion Matrix, Accuracy, and ROC AUC Score, with a primary focus on ROC AUC Score. This metric, widely recognized and employed, offers a comprehensive measure of performance and is visually represented in plots to depict the models' comparative performances.

4.1.1 Accuracy

Accuracy, as a performance metric, gauges the proportion of correct predictions relative to the total number of input samples. It excels when the dataset exhibits a balanced distribution of samples across different classes. However, it can be deceptive in scenarios with imbalanced class distributions. For example, imagine a training set comprising 98% of class A samples and only 2% of class B samples. In such a case, a model could attain a high accuracy of 98% by merely predicting every training sample as belonging to class A. Yet, when this same model is applied to a test set with a different class distribution, say 60% class A and 40% class B, the accuracy drops to 60%. While classification accuracy is a valuable metric, it can mislead us into believing we have achieved high precision, especially in imbalanced datasets.

$$Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of Correct predictions}}{\text{Total number of prediction made}} \quad 4.1$$

4.1.2 Recall

Recall, also known as sensitivity or true positive rate, is calculated by dividing the number of correctly identified positive samples by the total number of actual positive samples that should have been recognized. In other words, it measures the model's ability to capture and correctly classify all positive instances in a dataset.

$$Recall = \frac{TruePositives}{TruePositives + FalseNegatives} \quad 4.2$$

4.1.3 Precision

Precision is calculated by dividing the number of correctly identified positive samples by the total number of positive samples that the classifier predicted. It measures the accuracy of the model in correctly identifying positive instances among the ones it predicted as positive. In essence, it quantifies how many of the positive predictions made by the model are correct.

$$Precision = \frac{TruePositives}{TruePositives + FalsePositives} \quad 4.3$$

4.1.4 F1-Score

The F1 score is a metric used to evaluate the overall accuracy of a classification test. It represents the harmonic mean between recall and precision, providing insight into both the precision and recall of the classification. The F1 score is particularly useful when you want to balance the trade-off between precision and recall (Chicco *et al.*, 2020). If a model has high precision but low recall, it implies that it achieves high accuracy but may miss a significant number of relevant instances. Conversely, a high recall but low precision indicates that it captures many relevant instances but may also include a large number of false positives. Hence, a higher F1 score indicates better model performance, balancing the trade-off between precision and recall. It can be calculated using the following formula:

$$Accuracy = 2 * \frac{1}{\frac{1}{precision} + \frac{1}{Recall}} \quad 4.4$$

4.1.5 Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix provides a comprehensive breakdown of a model's performance, especially in binary classification problems where there are two classes, such as TRUE or False, YES or NO. It is a valuable tool for assessing the accuracy of a classification model (Hong *et al.*, 2021).

	Actually Positive (1)	Actually Negative (0)
Predicted Positive (1)	True Positives (TPs)	False Positives (FPs)
Predicted Negative (0)	False Negatives (FNs)	True Negatives (TNs)

Image source: <https://glassboxmedicine.com/2019/02/17/measuring-performance-the-confusion-matrix/>

The four important terms we have are True Positives, True Negatives, False Positives, and False Negatives.

- True Positives: this is the case where the algorithm predicted YES and the true output came out YES.
- True Negatives: this is the case where the algorithm predicted NO, and the true output came out NO.
- False Positives: this is the case where the algorithm predicted YES and the true output came out NO.
- False Negatives: this is the case where the algorithm predicted NO, and the true output came out YES. The accuracy of the confusion matrix can be calculated by

$$Accuracy = \frac{TruePositive + TrueNegative}{TotalSample}$$

4.1.6 Roc AuC Score

The ROC AUC Score, which stands for Receiver Operating Characteristics Area under Curve Score, is a commonly used metric for assessing the performance of a classification model (Hong *et al.*, 2020). The ROC AUC Score measures the severability of classes and indicates how well the model can distinguish between different classes. In classification problems, performance is often evaluated by varying the decision threshold for classifying instances. A superior model should be able to accurately predict class 0 as 0 and class 1 as 1. This ability is reflected in a high ROC AUC score. The ROC is a graphical representation of the model's performance. It plots the True Positive Rate (TPR) on the y-axis and the False Positive Rate (FPR) on the x-axis. The ROC AUC Score quantifies the area under this curve, providing a numerical measure of how well the model performs in terms of class separation.

$$\text{TruePositive, Recall, Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad 4.5$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad 4.6$$

$$\text{FalsePositiveRate} = 1 - \text{Specificity} = \frac{FP}{TN + FP} \quad 4.7$$

At this point, we present the results obtained from various machine learning models, each applied to the same processed data. These results are compared to determine the best predictive model. The primary evaluation metric used for this comparison is the AUC score, although other metrics are also considered to provide a comprehensive assessment of each model's performance. The AUC, or Area under the Curve, represents the probability that a model will rank a randomly selected positive instance higher than a randomly chosen negative instance. In essence, it measures the model's ability to discriminate between positive and negative instances (Hong *et al.*, 2020). A higher AUC score indicates a better-performing model in terms of its capability to predict all outcomes effectively. It establishes a clear boundary between the positive and negative classes, making it a valuable metric for assessing model strength in differentiating between two outcomes.

4.3 Parameter Tuning With the Best Model

As a measure to improve the predictive capacity of our baseline model, we conducted hyperparameter tuning using the PSO method, which serves as a crucial step in optimizing learning algorithms.

4.4 Comparative Analysis

Our evaluation considered the original dataset, utilizing the AUC score, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score for comparison. The SVC and PSO-tuned SVC, are all evaluated. The PSO-tuned SVC consistently outperformed other models on all evaluation metrics. Table 4.2 reveals that out of all sample cases, PSO-tuned SVC identified more anxiety case more correctly.

Table 4.2: Accuracy, Precision and AUC score after hyperparameter tuning after comparing the results of how each algorithm performed based on the metrics.

Methods	Accuracy	Precision	AUC score	Recall	F1 score
Support Vector Classifier	0.862	0.822	0.7200	0.6730	0.7010
PSO-based Support vector classifier	0.960	0.960	0.9882	0.9980	0.8933

Figure 4.1: Visualization of the comparative measures employed. Showing the consistent superiority of the PSO model over the baseline SVC model.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The primary aim of this study was to explore the application of machine learning models, with a specific focus on Support Vector Machines (SVMs), in predicting anxiety treatment outcomes. The foundation of the research lies in the recognition of the complex nature of mental health and the potential for personalized intervention strategies. The study employs a holistic approach by incorporating various features, including psychological scores, demographic information, and treatment history, to comprehensively understand the factors influencing treatment efficacy. Notably, the models developed

undergo optimization through hyperparameter tuning techniques such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), showcasing the potential to enhance predictive accuracy. The study emphasizes the transformative role of advanced machine learning methodologies in gaining deeper insights into the intricate interplay of variables affecting anxiety treatment outcomes. The methodology employed in this research involves the development and optimization of predictive models, particularly the Support Vector Classifier, tuned using the PSO technique. The result suggest that the PSO-tuned Support Vector Classifier did well to model well the relationship over the regular models over all metric measures employed. This study also underscores the importance of collaboration between data scientists, clinicians, and mental health professionals for the responsible deployment of machine learning models in clinical settings. Overall, the research lays the foundation for future endeavours in refining and advancing predictive analytics for personalized and effective anxiety treatment strategies.

REFERENCES

- Anxiety*. (n.d.). <https://www.apa.org>. <https://www.apa.org/topics/anxiety> Lane, R. (2021, October). DévoraKestel: global leader in mental health policy. *The Lancet*, 398(10308), 1295. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(21\)02148-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(21)02148-6)
- Aburto, J. M., Schöley, J., Kashnitsky, I., Zhang, L., Rahal, C., Missov, T. I., Mills, M. C., Dowd, J. B., & Kashyap, R. (2021, September 26). Quantifying impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic through life-expectancy losses: a population-level study of 29 countries. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, 51(1), 63–74. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyab207>
- A Review on Imbalanced Data Handling Using Undersampling and Oversampling Technique. (2017, May 2). *International Journal of Recent Trends in Engineering and Research*, 3(4), 444–449. <https://doi.org/10.23883/ijrter.2017.3168.0uwxm>
- A, Ch.Swetha, Dr. Mahesh Kotha, & D Anusha. (2022, June 1). A Systematic Review on Machine Learning Algorithms for Diagnosis of Diabetes in Health Care Systems. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, 422–433. <https://doi.org/10.32628/ijrst229394>
- ArchitSisodia. (2022, June 18). House Price Prediction based on ML using Regression Techniques. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology*, 548–553. <https://doi.org/10.48175/ijarsct-4854>
- Author commentary on Hideki Ishikawa et al. (2023, March 29). *Endoscopy*, 55(04), v10–v10. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1956-7292>
- Albrecht, K. (2007, March 1). Re: “A Security Analysis of the VeriChip Implantable RFID Device” JAMIA PrePrint: Accepted Article. Published August 23, 2006 as doi:10.1197/jamia.M2143. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 14(2), 249–250. <https://doi.org/10.1197/jamia.m2316>
- Chong, K., & Shah, N. (2022). Comparison of Naive Bayes and SVM Classification in Grid-Search Hyperparameter Tuned and Non-Hyperparameter Tuned Healthcare Stock Market Sentiment Analysis. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 13(12). <https://doi.org/10.14569/ijacsa.2022.0131213>
- Chicco, D., & Jurman, G. (2020, January 2). The advantages of the Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) over the F1 score and accuracy in binary classification evaluation. *BMC Genomics*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-019-6413-7>

Charbuty, B., & Abdulazeez, A. (2021, March 24). Classification Based on Decision Tree Algorithm for Machine Learning. *Journal of Applied Science and Technology Trends*, 2(01), 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.38094/jastt20165>

Data Science and Ethics. (2020, September). *Computer Engineering and Intelligent Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.7176/ceis/11-5-02>

Dadashi, H., & Mohammadi, M. (2023, October). Random update particle swarm optimizer (RUPSO): A novel robust optimization algorithm. *Structures*, 56, 104933. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2023.104933>

Fearn, T. (2004, October). Support Vector Machines I: The Support Vector Classifier. *NIR News*, 15(5), 14–15. <https://doi.org/10.1255/nirn.788>

Foltýnek, T., Meuschke, N., & Gipp, B. (2019, October 16). Academic Plagiarism Detection. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 52(6), 1–42. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3345317>

George, A. S., Kurup, A. V., Balachandran, P., Nair, M., Gopinath, S., Kumar, A., & Parasuram, H. (2021, July 2). Predicting Autonomic Dysfunction in Anxiety Disorder from ECG and Respiratory Signals Using Machine Learning Models. *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (IJOE)*, 17(07), 143.

Hong, C. S. (2021, March 31). Confusion plot for the confusion matrix. *Journal of the Korean Data and Information Science Society*, 32(2), 427–437. <https://doi.org/10.7465/jkdi.2021.32.2.427>

Hong, C. S., & Choi, S. Y. (2020, July 31). ROC curve generalization and AUC. *Journal of the Korean Data and Information Science Society*, 31(4), 477–488. <https://doi.org/10.7465/jkdi.2020.31.4.477>

Hong, L., Yu, X., Wang, B., Woodward, J., & Özcan, E. (2023, April). An improved ensemble particle swarm optimizer using niching behaviour and covariance matrix adapted retreat phase. *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, 78, 101278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2023.101278>

Islam, M. M., Haque, M. R., Iqbal, H., Hasan, M. M., Hasan, M., & Kabir, M. N. (2020, September). Breast Cancer Prediction: A Comparative Study Using Machine Learning Techniques. *SN Computer Science*, 1(5). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-020-00305-w>

Jacobson, N. C., Lekkas, D., Huang, R., & Thomas, N. (2021, March). Deep learning paired with wearable passive sensing data predicts deterioration in anxiety disorder symptoms across 17–18 years. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 282, 104–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2020.12.086>

Kriebel, J., & Stitz, L. (2020). Deep Learning: Credit Default Prediction from User-Generated Text. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3523083>

Kilichev, D., & Kim, W. (2023, August 29). Hyperparameter Optimization for 1D-CNN- Based Network Intrusion Detection Using GA and PSO. *Mathematics*, *11*(17), 3724. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math11173724>

Kong, F., Jiang, J., & Huang, Y. (2019, June 6). An Adaptive Multi-Swarm Competition Particle Swarm Optimizer for Large-Scale Optimization. *Mathematics*, *7*(6), 521. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math7060521>

Khan, A., Uddin, R., Alam, N., Sultana, S., Alam, M. U., & Ahmed, R. (2020, October 23). Psychometric properties of the Bangla version of the Kessler Psychological Distress Scale (K6). *GLOBAL PSYCHIATRY ARCHIVES*, *2*(2), 183–194. <https://doi.org/10.52095/gpa.2020.1333>

Kumar, P., Garg, S., & Garg, A. (2020). Assessment of Anxiety, Depression and Stress using Machine Learning Models. *Procedia Computer Science*, *171*, 1989–1998. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.04.213>

Li, R., & Bilal, U. (2021, June). Interactive web-based data visualization with R, Plotly, and Shiny (Carson Sievert). *Biometrics*, *77*(2), 776–777. <https://doi.org/10.1111/biom.13474>

Magson, N. R., Freeman, J. Y. A., Rapee, R. M., Richardson, C. E., Oar, E. L., & Fardouly, J. (2020, October 27). Risk and Protective Factors for Prospective Changes in Adolescent Mental Health during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, *50*(1), 44–57. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-020-01332-9>

Manchia, M., Gathier, A. W., Yapici-Eser, H., Schmidt, M. V., de Quervain, D., van Amelsvoort, T., Bisson, J. I., Cryan, J. F., Howes, O. D., Pinto, L., van der Wee, N. J., Domschke, K., Branchi, I., & Vinkers, C. H. (2022, February). The impact

Menzies, R. E., & Menzies, R. G. (2020). Death anxiety in the time of COVID-19: theoretical explanations and clinical implications. *The Cognitive Behaviour Therapist*, *13*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1754470x20000215>

Menzies, R. E., & Menzies, R. G. (2020). Death anxiety in the time of COVID-19: theoretical explanations and clinical implications. *The Cognitive Behaviour Therapist*, *13*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1754470x20000215>

Ma, N., Furber, G., Roberts, R., & Winefield, H. (2015, November 30). Caregiver perceptions of mental health problems and treatment utilisation in siblings of children with mental health problems. *Journal of Mental Health*, 25(2), 165–168. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09638237.2015.1101413>

Nasir, J. A., Khan, O. S., & Varlamis, I. (2021, April). Fake news detection: A hybrid CNN-RNN based deep learning approach. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 1(1), 100007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjime.2020.100007>

Nemesure, M. D., Heinz, M. V., Huang, R., & Jacobson, N. C. (2021, January 21). Predictive modelling of depression and anxiety using electronic health records and a novel machine learning approach with artificial intelligence. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-81368-4>

OECD. (n.d.). https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/view/?ref=128_1282875agkkojaa&title=The-territorial-impact-of-covid-19-managing-the-crisis-across-levels-of-government of the prolonged COVID-19 pandemic on stress resilience and mental health: A critical review across waves. *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, 55, 22–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.euroneuro.2021.10.864>

Oginni, O. A., Oloniniyi, I. O., Ibigbami, O., Ugo, V., Amiola, A., Ogunbajo, A., Esan, O., Adelola, A., Daropale, O., Ebuka, M., & Mapayi, B. (2021, August 26). Depressive and anxiety symptoms and COVID-19-related factors among men and women in Nigeria. *PLOS ONE*, 16(8), e0256690. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256690>

Pintelas, P., Kotsilieris, T., Livieris, I. E., & Pintelas, E. (2020). Predicting anxiety disorders and suicide tendency using machine learning: a review. *International Journal of Medical Engineering and Informatics*, 12(6), 599. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijmei.2020.10032888>

Pyrovolakis, K., Tzouveli, P., & Stamou, G. (2022, January 29). Multi-Modal Song Mood Detection with Deep Learning. *Sensors*, 22(3), 1065. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22031065>

Pintelas, P., Kotsilieris, T., Livieris, I. E., & Pintelas, E. (2020). Predicting anxiety disorders and suicide tendency using machine learning: a review. *International Journal of Medical Engineering and Informatics*, 12(6), 599. <https://doi.org/10.1504/ijmei.2020.10032888>

Paddy Disease Detection using Colour Co-occurrence Features and Support Vector Machine Classifier. (2020, May 2). *Journal of Xidian University*, 14(5). <https://doi.org/10.37896/jxu14.5/026>

- Pandit, M., Azwaan, M., Wani, S., Abubakar Ibrahim, A., AbdulmollaAbdulghafor, R. A., &Gulzar, Y. (2023, January 28). Examining Factors for Anxiety and Depression Prediction. *International Journal on Perceptive and Cognitive Computing*, 9(1), 70–79. <https://doi.org/10.31436/ijpcc.v9i1.368>
- Priya, A., Garg, S., &Tigga, N. P. (2020). Predicting Anxiety, Depression and Stress in Modern Life using Machine Learning Algorithms. *Procedia Computer Science*, 167, 1258–1267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.03.442>
- Raquib, A., Raquib, R., Jamil, S., Hossain, A., al-Mamun, F., &Mamun, M. A. (2022, June 6). Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices Toward the Prevention of COVID-19 in Bangladesh: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Frontiers in Medicine*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2022.856156>
- RABII, N. (2021, October 1). https://www.ijherjournal.com/journaldetail/comparative-religions-reality-and-challenges-methodological-approach_118#:~:text=COMPARATIVE%20RELIGIONS%2C%20REALITY%20AND%20CHALLENGES%3A%20METHODODOLOGICAL%20APPROACH. *International Journal of Humanities and Educational Research*, 03(05), 213–224. <https://doi.org/10.47832/2757-5403.5-3.19>
- Rodríguez, N., López, D., Fernández, A., García, S., & Herrera, F. (2021, July). SOUL: Scala Oversampling and Undersampling Library for imbalance classification. *SoftwareX*, 15, 100767. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2021.100767>
- Syafei, R. M., &Efrilianda, D. A. (2023, September 29). Machine Learning Model Using Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) Feature Importance and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) to Improve Accurate Prediction of Bankruptcy. *Recursive Journal of Informatics*, 1(2), 64–72. <https://doi.org/10.15294/rji.v1i2.71229>
- Stulz, N., &Crits-Christoph, P. (2010, August 2). Distinguishing anxiety and depression in self-report: purification of the Beck anxiety inventory and Beck depression inventory-II. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 66(9), 927–940. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.20701>
- Shi, M., & Shen, W. (2022, September 7). Automatic Modeling for Concrete Compressive Strength Prediction Using Auto-Sklearn. *Buildings*, 12(9), 1406. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12091406>

Saifullah, S., Fauziyah, Y., & Aribowo, A. S. (2021, February 24). Comparison of machine learning for sentiment analysis in detecting anxiety based on social media data. *Jurnal Informatika*, 15(1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.26555/jifo.v15i1.a20111>

Umar, M. A., Chen, Z., & Liu, Y. (2021). A Hybrid Intrusion Detection with Decision Tree for Feature Selection. *Information & Security: An International Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.11610/isij.4901>

Wei, Z., Wang, X., Ren, L., Liu, C., Liu, C., Cao, M., Feng, Y., Gan, Y., Li, G., Liu, X., Liu, Y., Yang, L., & Deng, Y. (2023, September). Using machine learning approach to predict depression and anxiety among patients with epilepsy in China: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 336, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2023.05.043>

Widodo, S., Brawijaya, H., & Samudi, S. (2022, October 3). Stratified K-fold cross-validation optimization on machine learning for prediction. *Sinkron*, 7(4), 2407–2414. <https://doi.org/10.33395/sinkron.v7i4.11792>

Yurduseven, S. (2023, March 30). <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/3050423>. *Tetik*, 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.55709/tetikdergisi.2023.3.56>

Zhang, R., Peng, X., Song, X., Long, J., Wang, C., Zhang, C., Huang, R., & Lee, T. M. C. (2022, February 14). The prevalence and risk of developing major depression among individuals with subthreshold depression in the general population. *Psychological Medicine*, 53(8), 3611–3620. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0033291722000241>

Zhang, C., Lei, X., & Liu, L. (2021, April 13). Predicting Metabolite–Disease Associations Based on LightGBM Model. *Frontiers in Genetics*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2021.660275>

Zhao, Q., & Li, C. (2020). Two-Stage Multi-Swarm Particle Swarm Optimizer for Unconstrained and Constrained Global Optimization. *IEEE Access*, 8, 124905–124927. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2020.3007743>

Zhu, Y., Jia, C., Li, F., & Song, J. (2020, March). Inspector: a lysine succinylation predictor based on edited nearest-neighbour undersampling and adaptive synthetic oversampling. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 593, 113592. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ab.2020.113592>

Zhang, L., Wang, S., & Liu, B. (2018, March 30). Deep learning for sentiment analysis: A survey. *WIREs Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 8(4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1253>